

ESI-MS Report

University
of Basel

Department of
Chemistry

Sample Information

Acquired by	: System Administrator
Date Acquired	: 13.02.2020 13:14:38
Sample Name	: ARN039
Sample ID	: ARN039
Data File	: ARN039_ARN039_002.lcd
Method File	: Only MS Autosampler.lcm
Original Method File	: Only MS Autosampler.lcm
Report Format File	: Fabian_Layout_NEW_3.lsr
Tuning File	: 190624.lct
Processed by	: System Administrator
Date Processed	: 13.02.2020 13:17:38

Method

<<Header>>

Generated	: 27.03.2019 11:36:14
Modified	: 13.02.2020 13:08:27

<<MS Parameter>>

Initial Valve Position	: -
--Segment 1 Event 1--	
Start Time	: 0.00 min
End Time	: 3.00 min
Acquisition Mode	: Profile
Polarity	: Positive
Event Time	: 0.50 sec
Detector Voltage	: +1.10 kV
Start m/z	: 100.00
End m/z	: 1000.00
Scan Speed	: 1875 u/sec
Interface Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
DL Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
--Segment 1 Event 2--	
Start Time	: 0.00 min
End Time	: 3.00 min
Acquisition Mode	: Profile
Polarity	: Negative
Event Time	: 0.50 sec
Detector Voltage	: +1.10 kV
Start m/z	: 100.00
End m/z	: 500.00
Scan Speed	: 834 u/sec
Interface Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
DL Volt.	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	: Use the Data in the Tuning File

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)

MassPeaks:9

Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.017-0.167(3-21) Base Peak:857.16(4237139)

BG Mode:Averaged 1.967-2.383(237-287) Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan Zoomed View

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)

MassPeaks:9

Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.017-0.167(3-21) Base Peak:857.16(4237139)

BG Mode:Averaged 1.967-2.383(237-287) Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan Zoomed View

Line#:1 R.Time:----(Scan#:----)

MassPeaks:9

Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.017-0.167(3-21) Base Peak:857.16(4237139)

BG Mode:Averaged 1.967-2.383(237-287) Segment 1 - Event 1

Line#:2 R.Time:----(Scan#:----) MS Spectrum Negative mode
MassPeaks:2
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.025-0.175(4-22) Base Peak:312.81(578347)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.975-2.392(238-288) Segment 1 - Event 2

Line#:2 R.Time:----(Scan#:----) MS Spectrum Negative mode Zoomed view
MassPeaks:2
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.025-0.175(4-22) Base Peak:312.81(578347)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.975-2.392(238-288) Segment 1 - Event 2

Line#:2 R.Time:----(Scan#:----) MS Spectrum Negative mode Zoomed view
MassPeaks:2
Spectrum Mode:Averaged 0.025-0.175(4-22) Base Peak:312.81(578347)
BG Mode:Averaged 1.975-2.392(238-288) Segment 1 - Event 2

